

Reactions of the allylic substrate at a glance

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Abstract : The chemistry of the allylic compounds has played, an important part in organic chemistry. Rearrangements in the allylic substrate have been long known. Allylic rearrangements are often observed in bimolecular (S_N2) as well as in unimolecular substitution (S_N1) process. Many apparently spontaneous isomeric rearrangements of allylic compounds are also known. Because of the resonance stabilization of the allyl carbocation ($\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2^+ \leftrightarrow ^+\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$) nucleophilic substitution of the allylic substrate by S_N1 pathway is easy to occur. It is also observed that bimolecular nucleophilic substitution (S_N2) also occurs at a faster rate than the corresponding saturated analogues. S_N1' , S_N2' , S_Ni' mechanisms are also operated only to the allylic substrate.

Resonance stabilization of the allyl radical leads to the substitution at the allyl position via radical ($\text{CH}_2=\dot{\text{C}}\text{H}-\text{CH}_2 \leftrightarrow \cdot\text{C}\text{H}_2-\text{CH}=\dot{\text{C}}\text{H}$) pathway also. During addition of HX to the double bond of the allyl halides, regioselective products are obtained, the product distribution is condition dependent. [3,3]- and [2,3]-sigmatropic rearrangements are also found to occur.

Because of the versatile reactions of the allylic substrate, it is chosen to discuss its various reactions with possible mechanistic explanations in detail in the present article.

Keywords : Reactions, allylic compounds, mechanism.

Nucleophilic substitution of the allyl halide

Nucleophilic substitution occurs easily in the allyl halide via both S_N1 and S_N2 pathway. It is observed that allyl chloride reacts 79 times faster with I^- by the S_N2 process compared to *n*-BuCl in acetone at 50 °C. Similar result is also obtained when allyl bromide undergoes substitution via S_N2 process. This is because of the stabilization of the S_N2 transition state by the adjacent π -electron cloud with the 'p' orbital at the carbon atom under attack (Fig. 1).

For allyl halide an alternative mechanism other than S_N2 may be considered. The nucleophile may approach to the double bonded carbon atom (Scheme 1).

Such process is called S_N2' . Thus for allyl halides substitution may follow S_N2 or S_N2' pathway. Naturally the question about the mechanism arises (which

Transition state for S_N2 displacement of a primary halide (higher energy)

Transition state for S_N2 displacement of allyl bromide π -cloud interaction (lower energy)

Fig. 1. Stabilization of the S_N2 T.S. by the π -electron interaction.

Scheme 1. $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2'$ process.

mechanism is to be operated and where?). It has been found that for the non symmetrically substituted allyl halide the nucleophile attacks to the less hindered end of the allyl halides, regardless the process is $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ or $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2'$. This point is illustrated in Scheme 2.

Prenyl bromide (1) reacts with phenoxide ion (PhO^{\ominus}) via $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ pathway not via the $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2'$ pathway to yield the product (2).

Butenyl chloride (3) reacts with an amine by the $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2'$ process predominantly.

Isobutenyl chloride (4) also reacts with thiophenoxide ion (PhS^{\ominus}) preferably via $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2'$ process.

Scheme 2. $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ vs $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2'$ process in substituted allyl halides.

The reason comes from the steric factor as well as from the stability of the product. The nucleophilic attack occurs at the less substituted carbon atom (less sterically crowded) according to which the more substituted alkene (thermodynamically more stable) is formed preferentially.

$\text{S}_{\text{N}}2'$ process favourably occur over $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ at the allyl chloride when organocopper reagent (RCu) complexes with BF_3 is used (Scheme 3).

The copper first forms complex to the alkene and then transfer the alkyl group to the $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2'$ position as it gathers in the chloride.

Scheme 3. Reaction of the allyl chloride with organocopper reagent (RCu).

Now let the nucleophilic substitution at the allyl halide by an $\text{S}_{\text{N}}1$ process be considered. When an allyl chloride or an allylic compound bearing good leaving group undergoes nucleophilic substitution in a highly ionizing medium two products are formed. When the labeled allyl chloride (7) undergoes hydrolysis with water two different labeled products (8) and (9) are formed in equal amounts (Scheme 4). The product formation is clearly explained by the formation of the same delocalized carbocation (7a) as an intermediate from the halide. Allyl carbocation is stabilized through resonance for which the nucleophile (H_2O) can attack to both C_1 and C_3 of (7a) with almost equal probability. Such type of rearranged product is called $\text{S}_{\text{N}}1'$ product (Scheme 4).

The mechanism is not straight forward (Scheme 4) in some cases. The two structurally isomeric methyl allyl chloride viz. crotyl chloride (5) and α -methyl chlo-

 Scheme 4. Detection of S_N1' reaction by isotope labeling.

ride (3) yield the same products (10) and (11) (Scheme 5) by alkaline hydrolysis separately but with different yields.

Scheme 5. Formation of structurally isomeric products from structurally isomeric reactants in unequal amounts in allylic rearrangement.

We can not explain the product distribution here via the free carbocationic intermediate formation. Because, if the reaction proceeds via the free carbocationic intermediate then the same amount of products are obtained from the substrates (5) and (3) as in each case, the carbocation $[\text{CH}_2^+ - \text{CH} = \text{CH}_2]$ is a delocalized carbocation. The product distribution is explained by considering the ion pair intermediate (5a and 3a) (Scheme 6). The products spread in the direction of the starting material, which indicates the formation of intimate or tight ion pairs (5a and 3a), where the field effect of Cl^- increases the electrophilicity of the nearby carbon (by increasing (+) ve charge density) the nucleophile therefore majorly attacks to that carbon.

Scheme 6. Allylic rearrangement via ion pair intermediate formation.

Similar types of experimental results are shown in Scheme 7 which supports the ion-pair intermediate formation.

Scheme 7

However when the nucleophilicity of the approaching nucleophile become less as in the case of the hydrolysis of prenyl chloride (6) with water, solvent separated ion pair (6a and 6b) is formed in higher percentage. In such cases the carbocation becomes free for which the product (12) corresponding to the attack of the nucleophile to the more stable carbocation (6b) is formed in predominant amount (Scheme 8).

1° and allylic carbocation 3° and allylic carbocation (more stable)
Solvent separated ion pair

Scheme 8. Allylic rearrangement via solvent separated ion-pair.

Internal return (is the process where by an ion-pair intermediate returns to its covalent precursor) of a functional group has been observed in some allylic rearrangements, e.g. 1,1-dimethyl allyl chloride (4) which on acetolysis by acetic acid yields two acetates (13) and (14), and partly rearranges to prenyl chloride (6) (Scheme 9).

Scheme 9

Here the rate of isomerization (formation of prenyl chloride) is independent on the concentration of external Cl^- , depends only on the concentration of halide (4). This is in agreement with the ion-pair concept. The intimate ion-pair before separation of allyl cation and Cl^- ion partly collapses back to the covalent species. The Cl^- ion, having 'forgotten' its original position in the molecule, recombines with both the resonating cations (4a and 4b) forming products (14) and (6) (Scheme 10).

Scheme 10

Here a point to note that allylic rearrangement is studied only with allyl chlorides and not with allyl bromides or iodides. This is because of the fact that allyl bromides (iodides) remain in equilibrium with its isomer but the chlorides do not equilibrate (Scheme 11).

Scheme 11

So, for obtaining a clear cut result on a single well-defined starting material, the chlorides are the compounds to use.

Like $\text{S}_{\text{N}}1'$ and $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2'$ process $\text{S}_{\text{N}}1^i$ ($\text{S}_{\text{N}}1^i \equiv$ Substitution Nucleophilic Internal) process also takes place when allyl alcohols (15) and (16) are to react with SOCl_2 . Like $\text{S}_{\text{N}}1^i$

reaction the intermediate appears to be the ester (15a and 16a) which decomposes to form the products (17) and (18) (Scheme 12).

Regioselectivity of the allyl alcohol undergoing reaction with HX (X = Cl, Br, I)

Allyl alcohols react with HX (X = Cl, Br, I) to form allyl halides only by $\text{S}_{\text{N}}1$ pathway because of the stability of the allyl carbocation. Treatment of propenol (19) with

HBr gives the corresponding allyl bromide (20). Only one compound is formed because attack at either end of the allyl cation (19a) gives the same product (Scheme 13).

If the unsymmetrical allyl cation is formed in a reaction, a mixture of product is often formed. When 2-butanol (10) and 3-butanol (11) are heated with HBr two products 2-butenyl bromide (21) and 3-butenyl bromides (22) are formed in 4 : 1 ratio. Here the position of the nucleophilic attack (regioselectivity) is predicted by the steric factor. Nucleophilic attack is faster at the less hindered end of the allyl carbocation (21a) (Scheme 14).

Similar type of result is obtained when 2-methyl but-3-en-2-ol (12) is treated with HBr to form prenyl bromide (1). Here only one product is obtained by nucleophilic attack to the less substituted position of the carbocation (12a) (Scheme 15).

Similar type of regioselectivity is observed when HBr is added to isoprene (23) under thermodynamically controlled condition (Scheme 16). The allyl cation (12a) is attacked by Br^- at less hindered end to give the product prenyl bromide (1).

Scheme 12. $\text{S}_{\text{N}}1'$ reaction of allyl alcohol.

Scheme 13

Scheme 14. Regioselectivity of allyl bromides formation from allyl alcohols.

Scheme 15

Scheme 16. Addition of HBr to isoprene.

Allyl chloride formation from allyl alcohol without rearrangement

Regiospecific allyl chloride can be prepared from allyl alcohol (Scheme 17). The reaction occurs stereospecific manner also (Scheme 17).

Scheme 17. Regioselective allyl chloride formation from allyl alcohols.

This method is not applied to the secondary alcohol. Often a mixture of product is formed (Scheme 18).

Scheme 18

The problem was solved by using $\text{Cl}_3\text{C}-\text{C}(=\text{O})-\text{CCl}_3$ / PPh_3 . The reaction follows $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ pathway with a bit of $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2'$ pathway (Scheme 19).

Allylic halogenations

Allylic compounds are more reactive than saturated compounds in radical catalyzed halogenations and react selectively at allylic position because of the stable allylic radical. N-Bromosuccinimide (NBS) is used for allylic bromination in presence of radical initiators AIBN, Ph-

Pathway :

Scheme 19

COOOC-Ph etc. When cyclohexene (24) is heated with NBS in presence of AIBN cyclohexyl bromide (25) is formed in good yield (Scheme 20). NBS is used in stoichiometric amount and the radical initiator is used in a catalytic amount. Such chemo selective allylic bromination of olefins is called the Wohl-Ziegler process.

The function of NBS is to supply a low concentration of molecular Br_2 , which explains the preference of substitution over addition. NBS supplies bromine at very low concentration so both the reactions (substitution and addition) are reversible in first step. But in case of substitution process NBS further react with HBr thus replace it from the reaction site forcing the equilibrium towards product side (Scheme 21).

Again Br_2 may add to the double bond to give bromonium ion. But in such case the rate equation becomes, $\text{Rate} = k [\text{alkene}] [\text{Br}_2]^2$. With very low concentration of Br_2 the $[\text{Br}_2]^2$ term becomes negligible and the rate of addition becomes extremely small; substitution predominates.

When more than one allylic positions are available products mixture are obtained, the proportions of which is predicted by the relative stabilization of the radicals. When compound (26) is allowed to react with NBS products (27) and (28) are formed in predominant amount via the more stable free radical (26b) (Scheme 22).

Mechanism

Initiation

Propagation

2. Propagation :

Scheme 20. Allylic bromination by NBS.

Scheme 21. Substitution vs addition during reaction of cyclohexene with NBS.

For allylic chlorination SO_2Cl_2 is used. When cyclohexene (24) is photolysed in presence of SO_2Cl_2 , and peroxide (ROOR) cyclohexyl chloride (31) is formed

via a radical pathway (Scheme 23). At very high temperature ($\sim 300^\circ\text{C}$) propene (32) reacts with chlorine to give allyl chloride (33) via a radical pathway (Scheme 24).

Oxidation of allyl alcohol

Oxidation of allylic alcohol by the chromium reagents creates problems like epoxidation and isomerisation (*E* to *Z* geometry) to the double bond. Allylic alcohol (**34** and **35**) can be specifically oxidized by active MnO_2 under mild conditions (room temperature) in a neutral solvent e.g. DMF, CHCl_3 , acetone etc. (Scheme 25).

Scheme 25

Oxidation of the allylic C-H

Oxidation of the allyl position (in **40**) is done successively by SeO_2 . Depending on the reaction conditions enones (**41**), allylic alcohols (**42**) or allylic esters are formed. The reaction proceeds by an 'ene' reaction followed by a [3,2]-sigmatropic rearrangement and hydrolysis of a selenium ester (Scheme 28). Stereoselectivity arises

Tertiary allylic alcohols (**36**) when oxidized by Jones reagent ($\text{CrO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$) direct oxidation not takes place rather rearranges to an enone (**37**) (Scheme 26).

for gem dimethyl alkenes (**43**), product (**44**) is formed preferentially (Scheme 29). Trisubstituted alkenes (**45**) are oxidized selectively at the more substituted end of the

Scheme 26

PCC (Pyridinium Chloro Chromate) also do the same thing (conversion of **38** to **39**) (Scheme 27).

carbon-carbon double bond, which indicates the electrophilic character of the 'ene' reaction (Scheme 30).

Scheme 27

Allyl Grignard reagent

Allyl Grignard reagent in solution exists in two isomeric structures (I and II) of which the former predomi-

Scheme 28. Oxidation of allylic C-H by SeO_2 .

The stereo selectivity is explained by a cyclic T.S (43a) in the rearrangement step

Scheme 29

Scheme 30

ates, containing the more substituted double bond. But when such allyl Grignard reagents (46) are allowed to react with an electrophilic species (47), the product (48) corresponding to the minor component is obtained. The reason is in the reaction the major component actually

takes part but there is a shift of the double bond which can be aided by the formation of a six-membered cyclic T.S (47a) (Scheme 31).

Because of the isomeric structure of allyl Grignard reagents (49a and 49b) mixture of products (50 and 51)

Scheme 31. Reactions of allyl Grignard reagent with a ketone.

The products formation can be explained by the formation of bromonium ions (54a and 54b) (Scheme 35). Both the bromonium ion (54a) and (54b) are formed. The labeled bromine takes part in bridging, forming the bromonium ion (54b). It could be formed from (54a) through intramolecular attack by Br*, in either S_N² or S_N¹ manner. The ring opening of the bromonium ion (54a) and (54b) by H₂O gives the products mixture.

Sigmatropic rearrangement involving allyl group

When aryl allyl ether is heated, allyl phenol is ob-

tained. The allyl group migrates to the *ortho*-position if one is free (conversion of 58 to 59) but if both the *ortho*-positions are occupied then migration occurs to the *para*-position (conversion of 60 to 61) (Scheme 36).

The first step of such reaction is a pericyclic reaction, called [3,3]-sigmatropic rearrangement. For *ortho*-migration the reaction proceeds via a six centered cyclic T.S (58a) (Scheme 37).

When the *ortho*-positions are blocked (as in case of 60) the first step still consists in an *ortho*-migration lead-

Scheme 35

Scheme 36. Rearrangement of allyl ether (Claisen rearrangement).

ing to the *ortho*-substituted cyclohexadione (60a). Absence of hydrogen at the *ortho*-position prevents aromatization of (60a) and hence it undergoes further rearrangement through a cyclic six membered deformed T.S (60b) giving (60c) which finally aromatize to the phenol (61) (Scheme 38).

Examples of abnormal Claisen rearrangement (conversion of 62 to 64) (Scheme 39) and out of ring migra-

Scheme 37

Scheme 38

tion (conversion of **65** to **66** and **67** to **68**) (Scheme 40) of the allyl group in suitably substituted allyl aryl ether have been observed.

Abnormal product is formed from the normal product (4)

Scheme 39. Abnormal Claisen rearrangement.

Claisen-rearrangement also occurs in the allyl vinyl ethers (**69** and **70**) and for such cases the rearrangement is known as Claisen-Cope rearrangement (Scheme 41).

Scheme 40. Out of ring Claisen rearrangement.

Ester (**72**) of the allylic alcohol (**71**) also undergoes [3,3]-sigmatropic rearrangement in presence of a strong base e.g. LDA (Scheme 42). This reaction is known as the Claisen-Ireland rearrangement. But benzyl allyl ether (**73**) undergoes [2,3]-sigmatropic rearrangement to make a new carbon-carbon sigma bond at the expense of a carbon oxygen sigma bond (Scheme 43).

The nitrogen analogue of the aryl allyl ether (**74**) undergoes Claisen rearrangement on heating. The process is called Amino-Claisen or Aza-Claisen rearrangement (Scheme 44). Not only an aryl group but also an alkenyl group can participate in the Claisen rearrangement of allyl enol ethers (**75**) (Scheme 45).

Here the Claisen rearrangement occurs with a complete transfer of the stereochemistry from the reactant to the product. Such a stereo controlled transformation of an old stereo center into a new one is called a chirality transfer and in this case (conversion of **75** to **76**) it is 1,3-chirality transfer.

Scheme 41. Claisen-Cope rearrangement.

librium between allyl sulfoxides and allyl sulfenates lies on the side of the sulfoxide but the equilibrium can be pushed towards sulfenate by reduction of its O-S bond (Scheme 46).

The reaction can be used for the γ -alkylation of the allylic alcohol where alkylation would not be possible normally (conversion of **79** to **80**) (Scheme 47).

The [2,3]-sigmatropic rearrangement of alkoxy car-

Scheme 42. Claisen-Ireland rearrangement.

Scheme 43

Scheme 44. Aza-Claisen rearrangement.

Reaction of an allylic alcohol (**10**) with PhSCl gives sulfenate ester (**77**) which rearranges to sulfoxide (**78**) on heating via [2,3]-sigmatropic rearrangement. The equi-

banions (**82**) is known as Wittig rearrangement. The requisite carbanions can be prepared by trans metallation of a stannane (**81**) (Scheme 48).

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Scheme 45. Claisen rearrangement with chirality transfer.

Scheme 46

Scheme 47

Scheme 48. Wittig rearrangement

Suggested Reading

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